

ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF INCREASING PASSIVE ASPECTS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN THE ACTIVE STATE IN THE THEORY AND PRACTICE OF SPORTS AS A MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

(on the example of volleyball)

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Annotation: *this article discusses aspects of achieving results in the process of revealing the organizational and pedagogical foundations for achieving high efficiency in the physical education of students of a higher educational institution. At the same time, the results obtained during the study are presented.*

Keywords: *physical culture, physical training, physical qualities, physical training, technical training, gymnastics, athletics, swimming, tourism, sports games.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПАССИВНЫХ АСПЕКТОВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ В АКТИВНОМ СОСТОЯНИИ В ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКЕ СПОРТА КАК СРЕДСТВА ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ

Аннотация: *в данной статье рассматриваются аспекты достижения результатов в процессе выявления организационно-педагогических основ достижения высокой эффективности в физическом воспитании студентов высшего учебного заведения. В то же время представлены результаты, полученные в ходе исследования.*

Ключевые слова: *физическая культура, физическая подготовка, физические качества, физическая подготовка, техническая подготовка, гимнастика, легкая атлетика, плавание, туризм, спортивные игры.*

Introduction. Physical education and sports are an independent type of human activity, and its importance in the development of society is very diverse. At the same time, it has a certain influence on social production, the formation of a person as a person, and the development of mutual relations. As we know, the purpose of physical education in higher educational institutions is to provide support to the training of highly qualified specialists through special assistance.

Physical education at OO'U performs the following tasks in the process of education under the program:

- educating students to have high moral, willful and physical qualities, to be ready to perform tasks of personal and social importance, to conduct productive work at a high level;
- maintaining and strengthening the health of students, helping the proper formation and all-round development of the body, maintaining high work ability throughout the entire period of study;
- comprehensive physical training;

- professional-practical and physical training of students, taking into account the characteristics of their future work activities;
- improvement of sports skills of student athletes;
- educating students about the need for regular physical education and sports.

The purpose of the research: to justify the passive aspects of physical education of students in the theory and practice of sports as a means of physical education based on the volleyball sport.

The importance of physical education in OO'U is determined not only by its general social tasks, but also by its capabilities in solving some tasks related to professional training. The professional direction of physical education is to ensure adequate development of movement abilities, formation of practical movement skills and qualifications, as well as increase the body's resistance to adverse effects of the external environment.[1].

Physical education in OO'U is carried out during the entire period of study of students and is implemented in various forms. They are interrelated, complement each other and are considered a single process in physical education of students.[2].

Daily physical exercises are aimed at strengthening health, improving mental and physical work capacity, improving the health of students' academic work, living and recreation conditions, and increasing time reserves for physical education. Public health, physical education and sports events are aimed at making students and young people regularly engage in physical education and sports, strengthening health, and improving physical qualities. The educational material of the program will consist of theoretical and practical sections, taking into account solving the tasks of physical education of students. The content of the theoretical section of the program provides students with the acquisition of deep theoretical knowledge on the basis of the theory and methodology of physical education. The practical part of the program includes educational materials for all educational departments. It is aimed at solving specific tasks of physical education of students. The following sections are included in the training content of all educational departments: gymnastics, athletics, swimming, tourism, sports games.

The main principle in determining the content of work in different educational departments is a differentiated approach to the educational process. The essence of this is that the educational material is created for each educational department, taking into account the gender, physical development, physical and sports-technical preparation level of students. The course program includes theory, mandatory practical program material for all educational departments, professional-practical physical training, as well as special tools to eliminate deficiencies in health and physical development. In theoretical training, special attention is paid to the issues of medical control, self-control, and the theory of physical education, taking into account the deficiencies in the state of health of students. General and professional-practical physical training is carried out taking into account the functional capabilities of students. The most important thing in such training is to master the techniques of practical exercises, to eliminate the functional deficiencies of organs and systems, and to increase the working capacity of the organism. It is important to implement the principles of systematicity, lightness and individuality in the training sessions of this department, to strictly regulate the load and gradually increase it. Despite the fact that the classes in the special department have a health-restorative orientation, they should not be conducted only for the purpose of treatment. Teachers should strive to ensure that students in this department have enough comprehensive and special physical training, improve their physical development level and, as a result, be transferred to the preparatory educational department.

Students of the main medical group who have completed the necessary control exercises and criteria for admission to the appropriate department of this department are admitted to the training groups of the Department of Sports Improvement. Students with a set of qualities that meet the requirements of the chosen sport are admitted to this department.

These classes are conducted by highly trained teachers. They must be well aware of the state of health and physical fitness of each athlete.

The work practice of physical education departments shows that in recent years, most students have been admitted to the preparatory department to participate in general physical training groups and in groups where training is conducted according to the principle of improvement in the selected sport. Students are assigned to groups based on their readiness and, most importantly, their desire to engage in one or another sport[3].

The expediency of sports-oriented training has been confirmed by a number of experimental pedagogical and physiological studies. As early as 1956, the Department of Physical Education of the Bryansk Institute of Technology, while analyzing the work of physical education, came to the conclusion that general physical training exercises cannot solve all the complex of tasks facing the physical education of students.

A low level of activity of students in general physical education (GPE) classes was noted. In addition, due to the lack of sports training aimed at achieving high results in any sport, interest in sports activities is not instilled in such groups, and usually most students stop participating in physical exercises after the completion of the compulsory course. It is also noted that the trainings on UJT often affect the teacher's creativity, do not allow him to effectively use the knowledge of his specialty, which in many cases leads to a decrease in the pedagogue's qualifications [4].

The experience of the creation of sports, including volleyball-oriented training groups, helped to determine it, that students participate and the activity increased significantly. At the end of the second stage, 85-90% of the future specialists have improved the requirements of sports and the physical development and physical fitness. The methodological and special training of teachers has grown significantly. In addition, physical training of students on the principle of improvement, including the principle of improvement in the sports games, and volleyballs will improve the functional state of the body, improves the magnitude of the central nervous system, increases mental work, increasing the concentration of mental work, increasing the accumulation and stability.

The university knows that the student's interest in a particular sport (including volleyball) creates good conditions for the development of the curriculum on this training. Unfortunately, in educational, a single approach has been developed to teacher volleyball in educational institutions. Analysis of the documentation for questionnaire between OOOS and Physical Education shows that existing differences in the planning planning are also relevant not only to the size of the learning material, but also in the content.

Research materials and methods: The following exercises were selected for general and special physical fitness: 30 meters, 10 * 3 moccidone run, throw the ball to the tall, to lift the ball.

It was held to assess the level of development of 30 meters from the speed of speed. The running 30 meters was done from low start. The best result in two attempts was taken into account.

The 1,000-meter stalk has helped identify the level of development of resistance. The distance was taken into account to accurately.

Coordinate compliance the level of development of the bodies was determined by the results of moccidone run into 9 x 3 x 6 x 3 x 9 meters.

The complement of 1 kg of weight was used to assess the ball to the execution shoulder and the rapid ability of the hands muscle. The testing, the first condition of the original "Basic upright" did both manually throw the ball backward from the head. Growing out of the starting line, Bill Ulki to the sign that came to the ground. The best result in three attempts was taken to Kis.

The long jump from the place assesses the rapid efforts of the Ayoc muscles. It was held according to the overall accepted rules of calculating the length of the measurement. From the first condition of "standing", she was done to blew away as far as the palms could move forward from where the palms were forwarded. In order to be more orientation, the heel is drawn with a chalk. The best result in three attempts were taken into account.

1 minute was used to measure the resistance of strength bending muscles from waiting for a body. The original position is lying down on the knees, and the elbows touch the side of the sides, and the partner touches the floor, which is tested. The number of elbows is fulfilled with the elbows as soon as possible, with the reverse carcass, with reverse alaks with the order of the order.

Research results and its activist: The experience in the creation of volleyball-oriented training groups is significantly increased and 85-90% of the most popular experts were reflected in the performance of the requirements of sports and the physical development and physical fitness.

Conclusion. In higher educational institutions that do not specialize in the field of physical education, physical education is considered as the most important basic structure of the formation of the educational subject and the holistic development of the student's personality. It ensures the necessary level of development of socio-biological aspects of life activity in young people and creates conditions for various manifestations of students' creative activity. Physical education is considered a mandatory part of the pedagogical structure of education, it helps to harmonize the unity of the body and soul of students, ensures the formation of health, physical and mental peace and universal human values in them during training, increases the level of physical culture of students. Researchers studying the problem of physical education of young students say that students physical education should occupy a proper place in education and professional training .

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